

Synthesis and Biological Screening of substituted Thymolythiazolidinones and Thymolyazetidiones

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Thymol derivatives¹, 4-thiazolidinones² and 2-azetidiones³ possess a variety of therapeutic activities. A large number of antibiotics contain β -lactam moiety⁴. The present communication reports the synthesis of thymol derivatives of 4-thiazolidinones and azetidiones. The compounds have been tested for antibacterial and antifungal activity

p-Nitrosothymol⁵ (1) on condensation with ethyl chloroacetate, followed by the action of hydrazine hydrate yielded *p*-nitrosohydrazinocarbonylmethylthymol. The latter on condensation with different aromatic aldehydes yielded the azomethine derivatives (2). Compounds 2 on cyclocondensation with thioglycolic and thiolactic acid yielded 4-thiazolidinones (3Aa-o, 3Ba-o) and with thiomalic acid in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride yielded 4-thiazolidinones (3Ca-o). The four-membered β -lactam ring is introduced in 2 by cycloaddition of chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine to yield 2-azetidiones (4a-o).

Biological activities : Compounds 2-4 were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities at a dose of 50 μ g using DMF as solvent.

The antibacterial activities of all compounds (2-4) against *S. citrus* (zone of inhibition 11-26 mm), *B. mega* (10-21), *E. coli* (17-25) and *S. typhosa* (10-20) are comparable with the standard drugs ampicillin (20, 15, 21 and 15 mm respectively) and chloramphenicol (24, 26, 24 and 25 mm respectively). The antifungal activities of all compounds (2-4) against *A. niger* are also comparable with the standard drug gresiofulvin (23 mm).

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 435-IR spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Hitachi R-1200 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Elemental analyses were carried out with a Coleman analyser. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

p-Methoxybenzaldehydrazinocarbonylmethyl-4-nitrosothymol (2). **General method** : A mixture of *p*-nitrosothymol⁵ (1; 0.01 mol), ethyl chloroacetate (0.01 mol) in dry acetone

(20 ml) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (2 g) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The content was then cooled, poured onto crushed ice and the resulting *p*-nitrosocarbonylmethylthymol (I) was crystallised from ethanol, (75%), m.p. 48°.

Scheme 1 Reagents (i) $\text{ClCH}_2\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$, NH_2NH_2 , RCHO , (ii) $\text{SH-CH}_2\text{-COOH}$ and (iii) ClCOCH_2Cl , Et_3N

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| a, R = C_6H_5 | i, R = 2-OHC ₆ H ₄ |
| b, R = 3-NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ | j, R = 3-OHC ₆ H ₄ |
| c, R = 4-NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ | k, R = 4-OHC ₆ H ₄ |
| d, R = 2-ClC ₆ H ₄ | l, R = 4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ |
| e, R = 3-ClC ₆ H ₄ | m, R = 2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ |
| f, R = 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ | n, R = 3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ |
| g, R = 2,6-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ | o, R = 4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ |
| h, R = 3,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ | |

For compounds 3

3Aa-o, X = H 3Ba-o, X = CH₃ 3Ca-o, X = CH₂COOH

A mixture of I (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 5 h. The content was then cooled, poured in ice-water, and the resulting *p*-nitrosohydrazinocarbonylmethylthymol (II) was crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 164°; ν_{max} 3300, 3^o200, 1600, 1565, 1500, 1640, 1625 cm^{-1} .

A mixture of **II** (0.01 mol), *p*-anisaldehyde (0.01 mol) and ethanol was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The resulting solid was washed with 30% sodium bisulphite solution, dried and crystallised from aqueous ethanol to yield **2I** (81%), m.p. 134°; ν_{\max} 3 150, 1 640, 1 635, 1 620, 1 600, 1 575, 1 510, 1 500, 1 220 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.21–1.27 (6H, d, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$), 2.24 (5H, s, $\text{CH}_3 + \text{OCH}_2$), 3.05–3.27 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.2 (1H, s, N–CH–R), 6.66–8.04 (6H, m, ArH), 8.29 (1H, s, NH). Similarly, other compounds were prepared: **2a**, m.p. 131°; **b**, 127°; **c**, 115°; **d**, 139°; **e**, 129°; **f**, 119°; **g**, 114°; **h**, 125°; **i**, 141°; **j**, 123°; **k**, 134°; **m**, 118°; **n**, 127°; **o**, 113°.

2-(p-Methoxyphenyl-3(N)(p)-nitrosothymoxyacetamido)-5H-4-thiazolidinones (3AI). *General procedure*: A mixture of **2I** (0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.015 mol) was heated at 120° for 12 h. It was then cooled and triturated with 2*N* NaHCO_3 and the resulting solid was washed with excess water, dried and crystallised from ethanol-water (2 : 1) to yield **3AI** (63%), m.p. 112°; ν_{\max} 2 960 (CH asym), 2 855 (CH sym), 1 380 (CH def), 1 615, 1 570, 1 505 (C=C), 1 255 (C–O–C), 1 645 (C=O amide), 1 635 (N–H def + C–N str), 1 615 (N–H def + C–N str), 1 060 (C–N), 3 155 (NH), 1 695 (C=O), 1 570 (C–N), 700 (C–S–C); δ (CDCl_3) 1.22–1.33 (6H, d, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$), 2.93 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.0–3.6 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.027 (2H, s, OCH_2), 4.068 (3H, s, CH_2), 6.5–7.4 (6H, m, ArH), 6.2 (1H, s, N–CH–R), 8.00 (1H, s, NH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared: **3Aa**, m.p. 218°; **b**, 168°; **c**, 196°; **d**, 212°; **e**, 198°; **f**, 175°; **g**, 179°; **h**, 188°; **i**, 202°; **j**, 243°; **k**, 231°; **m**, 218°; **n**, 175°; **o**, 223°.

2-(p-Methoxyphenyl-3-N(p)-nitrosothymoxyacetamido)-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinones (3BI). *General procedure*: A mixture of **2I** (0.01 mol) and thiolactic acid (0.2 mol) was heated at 120° for 10 h. It was then cooled and triturated by 2*N* NaHCO_3 solution and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to yield **3BI** (63%), m.p. 118°; ν_{\max} 2 960 (C–H asym), 2 850 (C–H sym), 1 360 (C–H def), 3 050 (C–H) 1 610, 1 580, 1 510 (C=C), 1 255 (C–O–), 1 640 (C=O amide), 1 645 (N–H def + C–N str), 1 625 (N–H def + C–N str), 1 280 (C–N), 3 145 (N–H), 1 710 (C=O), 1 580 (C=N), 695 (C–S–C); δ 1.29–1.30 (6H, d, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$), 2.30 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.9–3.5 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.03 (3H, s, OCH_3), 1.851–1.856 (3H, d, CHCH_3), 4.2–4.8 (1H, m, CHCH_3), 6.2–7.7 (6H, m, ArH), 6.0 (1H, s, N–CH–R), 8.2 (1H, s, NH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared: **3Ba**, m.p. 247°; **b**, 240°; **c**, 218°; **d**, 205°; **e**, 193°; **f**, 182°; **g**, 243°d; **h**, 219°; **i**, 188°; **j**, 202°; **k**, 213°d; **m**, 213°; **n**, 191°; **o**, 225°.

2(p)-Methoxyphenyl-3-N(p)-nitrosothymoxyacetamido-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones (3CI). *General procedure*: A mixture of **2I** (0.01 mol) and thiomalic acid (0.015 mol) in the presence of anhydrous ZnCl_2 (1.0 g) was condensed at 160° for 2 h and then the temperature was

raised to 180° for 1 h. The product obtained was dissolved in 4*N* NaHCO_3 solution and filtered. The filtrate was treated with dilute HCl and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from 1,4-dioxane-ethanol to yield **3CI** (58%), m.p. 260°; ν_{\max} 2 965 (C–H asym), 2 855 (C–H), 1 365 (C–H def), 3 050 (C–H), 1 615, 1 573, 1 505 (C=C), 1 260 (C–O–C), 1 640 (C=O amide), 1 650 (N–H def + C–N str), 1 285 (C–N), 3 140 (N–H), 1 740 (C=O of acid) and 715 cm^{-1} (C–S).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared: **3Ca**, m.p. 270°; **b**, 260°; **c**, 310°; **d**, 300°; **e**, 282°; **f**, 265°; **g**, 245°; **h**, 278°; **i**, 290°; **j**, 300°; **k**, 245°; **m**, 255°; **n**, 295°; **o**, 235°.

4-(p-Methoxyphenyl-1-(p-nitrosothymoxyacetamido)-3-chloro-2-azetidines (4I). *General procedure*: To a well-stirred solution of **2I** (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) in dry 1,4-dioxane (50 ml) was added chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mol) dropwise at room temperature. The mixture was stirred for 24 h and kept for 2 days at room temperature. The precipitates of triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered and washed with dioxane. The contents were poured on crushed ice. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol to yield **4I** (67%), m.p. 145°; ν_{\max} 2 970 (C–H asym), 2 855 (C–H sym), 1 380 (C–H def), 3 040 (C–H), 1 240 (C–O–C), 1 640 (C=O amide), 1 625 (N–H def + C–N str), 1 325 (C–N), 3 160 (N–H), 1 510 (C–NO), 1 700 (C=O β -lactam), 820 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); δ 1.34–1.36 (6H, d, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$), 2.46 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.1–3.6 (1H, m, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$), 4.14 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.1–7.2 (1H, d, –CH–R), 8.6–8.7 (1H, d, CH–Cl), 7.3–8.4 (6H, m, ArH), 9.2 (1H, s, NH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared: **4a**, m.p. 143°; **b**, 148°; **c**, 131°; **d**, 161°; **e**, 154°; **f**, 139°; **g**, 135°; **h**, 151°; **i**, 166°; **j**, 147°; **k**, 161°; **m**, 137°; **n**, 140°; **o**, 161°.

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